

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF UNDERGRADUATES

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Introduction

Today, we live in a digital world. Internet technologies are playing a significant role in society. We use these technologies in most of the daily activities of our lives and as a result, we can say that we are living in a digital world today. Social networks, which also are a part of this technology revolution, are also playing a major role in different aspects of society. These platforms influence society in positive and negative ways. For people who engage in certain activities such as studying sometimes are impacted by social media. The main aim of the study is to investigate how social media sites influence the academic performance of the undergraduates of Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce (FMSC) in University of Sri Jayewardenepura (USJP).

Some of the previously published studies concluded that using social media negatively impacts on the students' academic performance. Therefore, many educational institutions and parents are a bit worried about their children and students who are spending too much time on social media sites. As a result, some institutions and instructors do not allow students to use social media during the study hours to avoid the negative impact on their academic performance (Hasnain, Nasreen & Ijaz 2015) (Bennett, Maton, & Kervin 2008). But, according to some other findings university educators also believe that by utilizing social media, the students can improve their academic performance by giving more opportunity to interact with the lecturers and peer students and it encourages to gather more knowledge (Rovai 2001).

These findings might vary when it comes to the Sri Lankan context. So, this study fills that gap by investigating the influence of social media on the academic performance of university students, within the Sri Lankan context.

Methodology

The researcher used a quantitative approach to perform the study and data was collected through a survey using an online form. Hundred and fifty-four undergraduates of the Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce in the University of Sri Jayewardenepura were selected as the sample of the study. Also, the researcher followed a cross-sectional study method which took a cross-section from the population and implemented the study and applied the conclusions to the whole population.

Instrument Development

The researcher adopted Social Media and Academic Performance of Students Questionnaire (SMAAPOS) which was published by Mowafy (Mowafy 2018). The researcher selected this survey because it was survey research conducted addressing the same type of population as this study (university undergraduates), as well as it also measured the relationship between the social media usage and the student's academic performance. Based on those two, the researcher believed that using this instrument would give adequate answers to the research question of the study.

Reliability and Validity of the instrument

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. The coefficient value of 0.62 indicated that the research instrument was relatively reliable. According to literature if the coefficient value of a certain instrument is greater than 0.50, that instrument is reliable to measure that variable (Osharive 2015).

Data Analysis

When considering the data analysis methods and techniques, researchers used descriptive analysis techniques to analyze the demographic information and advanced data analysis techniques to check the reliability and to answer the research question. The researcher used the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software to perform both descriptive and advance data analysis.

Results and Discussion

Major Findings of the Study

There is a negative relationship between social media usage and students' academic performance of FMSC, USJP students. According to the result of Correlation analysis (-0.62), the students who highly use social media obtain a lower GPA and the students with less social media usage obtain a higher GPA value.

Majority of the respondents accepted that they used social media initially for socialization activities. But a considerable number of students also use it for academic purposes as well.

According to the study, most popular social media platforms are WhatsApp, Facebook and YouTube. Apart from that the popularity of Twitter, LinkedIn and other types of social media are relatively low.

Most of the undergraduates use social media for two hours, three hours and one hour daily.

Conclusion

Practical implications

The students should create a balance between using social media as an entertaining tool and academic work.

There is an urgent need for introducing games and other types of entertaining activities which help to increase the knowledge level of students and encourage them to engage those types of activities during their free time.

Lecturers should encourage students to use social media as a tool for improving academic performance.

Limitations of the study and future work

This study was conducted by only using 154 respondents because of the time limitation and all the data were collected from the undergraduates in the Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce of the University of Sri Jayewardenepura. The researcher suggests that for future researches, there is a need to try to collect more

sample data from different faculties or even from different universities as those findings would be more reliable than the findings of this study.

In this study, the researcher used the number of hours spent in social media to measure “Social media usage” and use GPA value to measure “Academic Performance”. So, here researchers did not measure the students’ perception of whether social media usage affects their studies or not. It is better to measure students’ perception about this matter in future studies.

In this study, the researcher did not deeply consider how students can positively use social media. So, the researcher recommends future researchers to study “how students can use these types of media in a beneficial way to their academic activities”.

Also, in this study, the researcher only considered the students’ perspective, but future researchers should also investigate university lecturers’ perception of social media as a teaching tool in the higher education context.

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